

Early Signs of Autism in Children

Abstract

Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) is a neurodevelopmental disorder characterized by differences in social communication, behavior, and sensory processing. Early detection is critical, as intervention programs implemented before the age of three can significantly improve developmental outcomes. This paper reviews existing literature on the early signs of autism in children, focusing on social communication differences, repetitive behaviors, and sensory sensitivities. In addition, a brief survey was conducted to examine parental perceptions of when early signs of autism first appear. The results revealed a clear gap in awareness: parents of children with ASD were more likely to recognize that signs can emerge before age two, while parents without direct experience often identified later ages or expressed uncertainty. These findings highlight a lack of widespread public understanding of early developmental indicators. Therefore, this paper underscores not only the importance of early identification but also the urgent need for increased public education and awareness to promote timely diagnosis and intervention.

Introduction

Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) affects approximately 1 in 36 children in the United States (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2023). It is marked by challenges in social communication, repetitive behaviors, and restricted interests. While diagnosis can occur at any age, early identification of symptoms is critical for enabling timely interventions that improve language, cognitive, and social outcomes.

This paper examines early indicators of autism in children under the age of three, highlighting patterns in social, behavioral and sensory domains. The goal is to provide insight into early detection and encourage awareness among parents, educators and healthcare professionals. In addition to reviewing existing research, this paper also incorporates findings from a brief survey examining parental perceptions of when early signs of autism first appear. This combined approach provides both scientific and real-world perspectives on early identification.

Background / Literature Review

Early identification of ASD is supported by research indicating that children with autism often exhibit measurable differences before the age of three (Zwaigenbaum et al, 2015). The following categories summarize the most commonly observed early signs:

Social Communication Differences

- Limited Eye contact
- Lack of response to name
- Reduced social smiling or shared enjoyment
- Difficulty with joining attention (eg: pointing or showing objects)

Repetitive or Restricted Behaviors

- Hand flapping or rocking or other repetitive movements
- Insistence on routines or ritualized behaviors
- Intense focus on specific objects or topics

Sensory Sensitivities

- Overreacting or underreacting to sensory stimuli such as light, sound or touch
- Unusual interest in sensory aspects of objects (eg: spinning wheels or textures)

Early recognition of these patterns is essential as early intervention programs have been shown to significantly improve developmental outcomes in children with ASD (Rogers & Vimara, 2008). While these early indicators are well documented in research, less is known about how well they are understood by the general public, particularly among parents without direct experience with ASD.

Methods

This study combines a literature review with a brief survey to examine both established research and public perceptions regarding the early signs of ASD.

The literature review was conducted using peer reviewed journal articles, government reports and publications from reputable health organizations. Databases searched included Google Scholar, PubMed and Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) website. Sources were selected based on relevance, credibility and focus on early signs of ASD in children under three years of age.

In addition to the literature review, a survey was administered to gather data on parental awareness of early autism signs. This survey included 32 participants - consisting of 12 parents of children diagnosed with ASD and 20 parents with children without a diagnosis of ASD. Participants were asked one multiple choice question: “At what age do you think early signs of

autism can first appear?” Response options included: before 12 months, 12 - 24 months, 2 - 3 years, after 3 years and Not sure.

Responses were collected anonymously and analyzed using descriptive statistics to compare trends between the two groups. The results were used to identify differences in awareness and perception related to early ASD signs. No personally identifiable information was collected and participation was voluntary.

Results

Findings from Established Research

- Social communication differences are often observable between 6-12 months, including eye contact and lack of response to name
- Repetitive behaviors and restricted interests typically emerge between 12-24 months
- Sensory sensitivities may appear in infancy but vary in intensity and presentation
- Early identification is associated with improved developmental outcomes, particularly in language, social interaction and adaptive functioning.

Findings from Public Perceptions (Survey Results)

- Among parents of children with ASD (n=12), all respondents indicated that early signs can appear before the age of two.
- Nearly half of these participants identified ‘before 12 months’ as the earliest point of symptom appearance.
- Among parents without children diagnosed with ASD (n=20), responses were more varied.
- A significant portion selected later age ranges, such as 2-3 years or after 3 years, while other reported uncertainty
- Overall the data indicate a clear difference in perceived timing of early autism signs between the two groups.

At what age do you think early signs of autism can first appear?

Discussion

The findings from both the literature review and the survey highlight an important gap between established research and public perception regarding the early signs of ASD. Existing research consistently shows the early indicators of ASD can emerge within the first two years of life, with some signs observable as early as 6-12 months. These findings emphasize the importance of early detection in enabling timely intervention and improving developmental outcomes.

In contrast, the survey results reveal that awareness of these early signs is not consistent across all parents. Parents of children diagnosed with ASD demonstrated a stronger understanding of early developmental indicators, with all respondents identifying that signs can appear before the age of two and many recognizing infancy as a critical period. This alignment with established research suggests that firsthand experience with ASD may significantly increase awareness and recognition of early symptoms.

However, responses from parents without direct experience with ASD were more varied with many selecting later developmental stages or expressing uncertainty. This discrepancy indicates a potential lack of general awareness regarding the early onset of ASD symptoms. As a result,

some parents may not recognize early warning signs which could contribute to delays in seeking professional evaluation and intervention.

The contrast between these two groups underscores the importance of public education and early screening efforts. Increasing awareness among parents, caregivers and educators about the early signs of ASD could lead to earlier identification and access to support services such as Applied Behavior Analysis (ABA), speech therapy etc. Tools such as early screening checklists and guidance from pediatricians can play a critical role in bridging this knowledge gap.

Overall, these findings reinforce that though scientific understanding of early ASD indicators is well established, this knowledge is not fully reflected in public perception. Addressing this gap through education and outreach is essential to ensure that more children are identified early and receive the interventions that can significantly improve their developmental outcomes.

One limitation of this study is the relatively small sample size of the survey, which may not fully represent broader public perceptions.

Conclusion

This study emphasizes the importance of early identification of Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) by combining established research with survey findings. Research shows that early signs can appear within the first two years of life, making early recognition critical for effective intervention and improved developmental outcomes.

The survey revealed a gap in awareness between parents with and without direct experience with ASD, with the latter group often identifying later ages or expressing uncertainty. This highlights a lack of widespread understanding of early symptoms.

Overall, these findings underscore the need for increased public education and awareness to support earlier recognition, timely intervention and better outcomes for children with ASD

References

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